

Editorial

Need of Improved teaching and learning methods in medical education in India

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Introduction

Medical education in India is suffering from various implementation levels. It is implemented from a currently available resources and applying the traditional innovative procedures. To achieving higher standards, it's to advance in redesigned curriculum and teaching to produce skilled medical graduates which will helpful in delivering better healthcare service to the

Abstract

In Indian medical education, it's crucial need to develop curriculum and teaching methodology to produce skilled medical graduates which will helpful in delivering better healthcare service to the society. To improve the new technologies in teaching and learning in medical education that moves beyond replacing or amplifying traditional teaching. Collaborative institutional learning activity is much beneficial to the students with data and knowledge sharing to improve the skills of future medical experts. Institutional policies will encourage the positivity in faculty member to teach effectively. Traditional curriculum can be transformed to new-aged curriculum using the integration of new technologies in teaching methods towards standardization in medical education in our country.

Keywords: Medical students, learning activity, Institutional policies, Traditional curriculum, Healthcare.

society. Redesigning in Medical education is the most important factor to ensuring healthcare systems can meet present and future medical diagnosis needs. Current evidence suggests that, in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs), healthcare system improvements are necessary to ensure healthcare services can meet current and future population needs, including evolving epidemiological disease patterns, shifting

demographics, new infectious disease health threats and the health impacts of climate change.[1] Previous medical education reform efforts have been sporadic and limited to single medical universities in specific departments, and not comprehensive or widespread.[13]

Abrupt changes in medical education curricula during the pandemic resulted in efforts to incorporate more student-led learning activities. One of the benefits of online learning is that it facilitates collaboration between institutions, which reduces duplication and benefits large numbers of learners [2]. A recent study showed that student suggestions and translations of educational resources on the COVID-19 pandemic have had positive influences on student learning and reached wider audiences [3]. In another study, medical students participated in service learning which involved student participation in initiatives that contributed to healthcare in their local communities, such as collecting and distributing personal protective equipment and providing childcare for frontline workers [4].

Medical Education in India

In Indian medical education, current scenario demands the advancement in curriculum and teaching methods in medical education.

The students should be participated in direct communication with the local community to observe the problems in society. The activity in students in classroom is also the major advancement in getting acknowledgement to tackle the problems in patient population.

Need for Improvement

Innovative teaching and learning methods offer the promise of nurturing critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and clinical acumen-indispensable qualities in modern medicine.[5] Faculty development programs (FDPs) aim to improve education effectiveness according to the faculties' needs and the organization's policies [6]. FDPs provide situations for fostering the faculties' capabilities to be compatible with changing environments in educational systems and emerging advanced

educational strategies [6-9]. FDPs facilitate the professional development of faculty members and the personal growth of those who need to pursue a career as a medical educator or educational leader [10, 11].

A comprehensive faculty development program should be built for the effective teaching. Faculties should be trained by workshops, peer coaching and attaining/delivering the seminars. Institutions should encourage the faculties to develop the research and active teaching, sponsor them for attaining the faculty development programmes more effectively. Institutions should support the faculty member for new research to develop new methods or procedure in diagnosis or treatments. Collectively all of these institutional policies will encourage the positivity in faculty member to teach effectively and to excel in their respective role to service the patient populations. Faculty development programmes should include modern pedagogical approaches like questioning, demonstration, explaining, practical, collaboration methods, and are more activity-based. Collaborative institutional learning activity is much beneficial to the students with information sharing to improve the skills of future medical experts.

Integration of technology into medical curricula can catalyse the application of adult learning theory in medical education and help to transform the learning environment from solely a distributor of content and knowledge into a space which facilitates the learning process and the assessment of the learner.[13]

Traditional curriculum can be transformed to new-aged curriculum using the integration of new technologies in teaching methods towards standardization in medical education in our country.

Conclusion

Redesigning in Medical curriculum is the most important factor to ensuring healthcare systems can meet present and future medical diagnosis needs. To improve the new technologies in teaching and learning in medical education that

moves beyond replacing or amplifying traditional teaching. Collaborative institutional learning activity is much beneficial to the students with information sharing to improve the skills of future medical experts. Institutional policies will encourage the positivity in faculty member to teach effectively. Traditional curriculum can be transformed to new-aged curriculum using the integration of new technologies in teaching methods towards standardization in medical education in our country. Conclusively herewith stating that, if all of the above discussed modifications implemented altogether and results will be the brighter future of Indian medical education and service to patients' population.

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